

The Impact of Staff Training on Cataloguers' Job Performance in Academic Libraries in Maiduguri Metropolitan Council, Borno State.

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Abstract

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Introduction: This study investigated the impact of staff training on the job performance of cataloguers in selected academic libraries in Maiduguri Metropolitan Council (MMC), Borno State.

Method: The study adopted a survey research design. The population comprised all 13 cataloguers in the selected libraries. The study's objectives were to determine the level of job performance of cataloguers and the type of training programs available to them, as well as the impact of staff training on cataloguers' job performance in academic libraries in MMC. Three research questions were raised and answered in line with these objectives.

Results/Findings: The findings revealed that the level of job performance of cataloguers in academic libraries in MMC is moderate. The types of training programs available to them include in-service training, mentoring/coaching, and job rotation. Additionally, the findings indicated a significant positive impact of staff training on cataloguers' job performance in academic libraries in MMC.

Conclusion: The study concludes that staff training positively affects job performance among cataloguers.

Recommendations: The study recommends that library management adopt various training methods to keep cataloguers abreast of the latest developments in cataloguing practices, both locally and globally.

Introduction

Libraries, perform the functions of selection, acquisition, organization and dissemination of information resources. The organization of information resources is known as cataloguing and classification. Cataloguing is the process of preparing catalogue entries of an information resource using some or all bibliographic information of a document such as: title, author name, publisher, etcetera, to physically describe the document. On the other hand, Classification is the process of providing subject access point to a document and where it can be located on the shelf. The overall purpose of cataloguing and classification is to enable a library user to identify a document of one's interest on a given title, author or subject and to locate it on shelves.

Cataloguers are library personnel shouldered with the responsibility of organizing the library information resources acquired by a library in their different forms and format, for the users to: identify, locate, and access the needed information from the general collections. The major jobs or tasks of a cataloguer is to prepare catalogue records, assigning subject headings, copy cataloguing and others. All this is done to facilitate shelf arrangement of document and easy retrieval by users (John-okeke in Eyo ,2021).

Job performance (JP) otherwise known as task or work performance is a measurement of how well or how poor employees carry-out job(s) hired for and how promptly they meet their deadlines or requirements. In a definition by George, Okwu, and Ogunbode (2022) job performance is employee's capacity to perform effectively in agreement with the job requirements to achieve organizational goals and objectives. Job performance of a cataloguer is the combination of results and behaviour in the process of service delivery in libraries towards achieving the goals of libraries. The JP

of library staff can be low, moderate or high which may be influenced by certain factors such as work experience, leadership style in the libraries, training, etc.

According to Umeh, Maduka, & Bamidele (2022) the measure of job productivity in service organization like that of cataloguers can be challenging, in the sense that it is not only about quantity, but about quality and time spent. Quantity refers to number of items cataloguer can catalogue within a given period. Quality is the accuracy of the cataloguing work, how often do library workers identify wrongly classified materials and send them for re-cataloguing. Then timeliness refers to how long it takes the cataloguer to accomplish the task at hand resulting into either delay or promptness. Therefore, the job performance of cataloguers has serious implication on the realization of goal and objectives of libraries which is, meeting the information need of users among other objectives.

Cataloguers' job performance can be achieved through adequate familiarity with subject matter and the use of controlled vocabularies such as Library of congress subjects Headings, thesaurus and acquisition of certain skills such as subject and bibliographic analysis skill for effective organization of library collection for service delivery (Aina, 2004). In recent time, the task performed by cataloguers have changed, the traditional way of cataloguing is no longer fashionable, thus the expectation to transform themselves through training and development practices which is essential to meet up with the expectations of the changing roles.

The human resource is the greatest asset of any organization, which need to be enhanced or developed towards realization of the organization's goals and objectives. Literatures have shown that a way to enhance the performance of the human resources is through some designed programs, such as training.

Staff Training is a program that is designed to increase the technical skills, knowledge, efficiency, and value creation to do any specific job in a much better way. The purpose of training is to reduce error, supervision so as to enhance Job performance of employees. Training is also necessary for both new and old cataloguers to keep them updated with the latest trends and technologies that are needed to perform well on their job and to survive in a competitive environment.

The importance of Staff training on job performance of cataloguers cannot be over-emphasized. Staff training received by cataloguers will equip them to a large extent and will enable them to perform their job effectively. Lack of or inadequate training for cataloguers may result in unwanted situations such as: ineffective cataloguing practices and backlog. Howorth, Moor, and Size in Ezomo (2012) expressed that lack of professionally trained cataloguers are causes of backlog.

Despite the nature of cataloguing job and importance of cataloguing, studies have shown that cataloguers are rated low in terms of job performance. Such studies as that of Monyela (2019) and Madireg and Jane in Haliru and Sokari (2016) observed that lack of continuous professional development (CPD) in place to update the cataloguers' knowledge to cope with dynamic changes in cataloguing field seems to be the causes of low job performance. The consequences of Lack of staff training for cataloguers may render them ineffective thereby performing below expectation and will give rise to lack of interest in the cataloguing job and ineffective catalogue for information retrieval resulting in user frustration.

Statement of the Problem

A preliminary observation by the researcher showed that cataloguing personnel are performing below standard and their Information and Communication Technology (ICT) skill is low. Could this be due to lack of

staff training and development for renewed skilled? Secondly, studies abound on Impact of training on library staff job performance generally, but none to the best knowledge of the researchers on Impact of Training on cataloguers' Job performance in Academic Libraries in Maiduguri Metropolitan Council. It is against this backdrop that the researchers sought to investigate the impact of staff training on cataloguers' job performance.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are to determine

1. the level of job performance of cataloguers in Academic Libraries in MMC.
2. the staff training methods benefitted by cataloguers in Academic Libraries in MMC.
3. the impact of staff training and development on cataloguers' job performance in Academic Libraries in MMC.

Research Questions

The research questions are:

1. What is the level of job performance of cataloguers in Academic Libraries in MMC?
2. What are the staff training method(s) benefitted by the cataloguers in Academic Libraries in MMC?
3. What are the impacts of staff training on cataloguers' job performance in Academic Libraries in MMC?

Literature Review

According to Umeh, Maduka, & Bamidele (2022) the measure of job productivity in service organization like that of cataloguers can be challenging, in the sense that it is not only about quantity, but about quality and time spent. Quantity refers to number of items cataloguer can catalogue within a given period. Quality is the accuracy of the cataloguing work,

how often do library workers identify wrongly classified materials and send them for re-cataloguing. Then timeliness refers to how long does it take the cataloguer to accomplish the task at hand resulting into either delay or promptness. Madukoma, Bamidele, and Unegbu (2015) observed, that job performance measurement for cataloguers are: quality of work, high productivity, and ability to bring out initiative among other things. This is to say that, not only do cataloguers need high quality cataloguing practices but are also expected to be initiative in their job. Monyela (2019) adopted a case study design to study Cataloguing practices from creation to use in Cape Town Metropolitan Public Libraries, South Africa. Cataloguers and senior librarians were the population of the study, despite the fact that cataloguers are experienced in their work, catalogue records do not fully adhere to the cataloguing rules which may be likely due to lack of continuous professional development (CPD) in place to update the cataloguers' knowledge and cope with dynamic changes in cataloguing field. It was concluded that, Cataloguers need adequate training and development of different types to be able to perform their job efficiently and effectively.

Olurunsola (2007) observed that, training and re-training of cataloguers and indeed librarians are very important and must be of serious concern to employees and employers. Haliru and Sokari (2016) also identified training methods for creating proficiency and understanding Resource description and Access (RDA) to include: webinar, workshops, seminars/conferences talks by Librarians knowledgeable in RDA, visits to libraries using RDA, etc. Ajidajun (2017) is of the opinion that, on -the- job training like orientation/induction, mentoring is the most popular method of training employed in most Nigerian Libraries. Mentoring is a learning method by which experienced people took responsibility to train the younger ones that

needed occupational skill. Bello & Mansur (2011)'s findings revealed that cataloguers use three types of mentoring programs Supervisory (81%), Situational (19%) and Group mentoring (13%). A majority 94% of the respondents felt mentoring enhances their descriptive cataloguing skills and the confidence to use work tools. While another 97% felt mentoring could be used for skill development, succession plans and as stability factor in term of changes. Baro (2022) expressed that Job rotation "provide cross training and reduce boredom from monotonous repetitive task". It is used by library to enhance skill, productivity, develop new relationship". Njoku (2018) observed that seminar is a forum where issues are raised and explored, but not necessarily resolved. Shalmalmi, (2022) assessed the capacity building programmes for Library personnel in Adamawa State Nigeria through a survey. The study revealed that internal training, In-service training, job rotation and orientation were to high extent in libraries under study and that internal training which comprise of professionals, conferences, workshops, seminars, & computer training were to moderate extent.

A study by Adomi and Famola (2012) on Training and Development of Cataloguers in National Library of Nigeria, revealed that, 77.5% of the respondents agreed that staff development improves the quality of library staff and 92.5% staff training enables staff to become more competent and enhances job satisfaction and also observed that there will be fewer backlogs of unprocessed books if cataloguing and classification are properly understood by cataloguers. Saka and Haruna (2013) studied relationship between staff development and job performance among personnel in Branch libraries, University of Maiduguri and result revealed that formal education does not enhance JP while seminar, conference, workshop attendance enhances job performance of staff. Staff development

collectively increases the job performance of staff tend to be higher. Njoku (2018) in a study of professional development and performance evaluation for cataloguers in south-west Nigeria, observed that exposing cataloguers to courses increases their desire to excel and grow on the job better and impact significantly on their job performance. Bhat (2013) expressed that training is a useful means of coping with changes brought about by technological innovations and that it plays a key role in enhancing employee performance. Janet, Oluwatoyin, Ajiboye, Omosanya (2022) investigated staff development practices (SD) among librarians from three public university libraries in Ogun State, Nigeria. Findings indicated additional higher degree, seminar and conferences and in-house seminars are the most frequently patronized staff development practices among librarians. Staff training through different types of program help staff to

update their knowledge and skills thereby making them competent to perform well on their job. This is attested to, by writers like Ochinakpor, in Adeleke (2013) who observed that, professional development program like workshop, seminars enlighten cataloguers on the various aspects and problems associated with bibliographic work (cataloguing) and finding ways to solve them.

Research Methodology

The study adopted a survey design which is concerned with collection of data for the purpose of investigation. All cataloguers in the selected Academic Libraries in MMC formed the population of the study. A complete enumeration of the Population was considered because it was manageable. Table 1 below shows the breakdown of the population.

Table 1: Academic Libraries in MMC and Number of Cataloguers in the Libraries

Name of Libraries	Number of Cataloguers
College of Agric. Library, Maiduguri	3
Professor Umara Zulum Library, Ramat Polytechnic, Maiduguri	2
Ramat Library, University of Maiduguri.	8
Total	13

Source: Field survey 2024

A questionnaire was used for data collection. Tahir, Jain, Khan and Hashim (2014) and Eyo (2021) questionnaires were used with some modifications. The questionnaire for this study comprised of sections A and B. Section A is on demographic data; such as gender, age, educational qualification and years of experience and Library. Section B is divided into three sections (1-3) in accordance with the research questions raised. The questionnaire performance of Cataloguers in Academic Libraries

comprised of 23 items to elicit data on the research questions. A total of 13 copies of the questionnaire were administered with 100% response rate achieved and all found useable. The collected data were analyzed using frequency counts, percentages, means and standard deviation presented in Table form.

Data Analysis, Results and Discussion

Question one: What is the Level of Job Performance of Cataloguers of Academic Libraries in Maiduguri Metropolitan Council (MMC)

Table 1: Mean ratings on the level of Job

S/N	ITEMS	RESPONSES				Mean	Decision
		HE	ME	LE	NA		
1.	My ability to catalogue 15 or more books in a day is to:	11(84.6)	2 (15.38)	0(0)	0(0)	3.84	High
2	Possibility of receiving wrongly classified book for re-cataloguing is:	0(0)	0(0)	13(100)	0(0)	2.00	Low
3.	My supervisor’s satisfaction with the quantity and accuracy of my work to:	9(69.23)	4(30.76)	0(0)	0(00)	3.69	High
4.	My ability to classify 7 or more books in a day is to:	3(23.07)	5(38.46)	5(38.46)	0(0)	2.07	Moderate
5.	Possibility of Books staying longer than necessary without being catalogued is to:	0(0)	2 (15.38)	11(84.6)	0(0)	2.15	Moderate
6.	My chances of using online catalogue is to:	0(0)	0(0)	8(61.53)	5(38.46)	1.6	Low
7.	My skill of using library software for cataloging is to:	0(0)	0(0)	8(61.53)	5(38.46)	1.60	Low

Source: Field survey 2024

Key: HE=High Extent. ME-Moderate Extent, LE=Low Extent, NE=Never Ability

Decision Rule: Mean: 2.50= moderate, above 2.50= high, below 2.50=low.

Results in table 1 shows that item number one: my ability to catalogue 15 or more books in a day is high with a mean of 3.84. Possibility of

receiving wrongly classified book for re-cataloguing has a mean of 2.07. My supervisor’s satisfaction with the quantity and quality of my work has a mean 3.2. Library users’ satisfaction with our catalogue has a mean of3.69. My ability to classify seven 7 or more books in a day (mean =2.07). Possibility of Books staying longer than necessary in

cataloguing section without being processed (mean=2.15). My chance of copying catalogue entry online (mean=1.60). My chance of using library software for cataloguing(mean=1.60).

The analysis revealed that out of eight statements, three of them were to high extent as their mean scores were above the bench mark mean of 2.50 criterion point on a four-point

adopted Likert scale which indicated high extent. On the other hand, five items were low extent with mean scores below the bench mark mean of 2.50 criterion point on a four adopted Likert scale. Therefore, job performance of the respondents is of moderate level.

Question 2. What are the Types of Training Available for Cataloguers in Academic libraries in MMC?

Table 2: Types of Training available for Cataloguers in Academic libraries in MMC

		RESPONSES		Total
S/N	ITEMS	YES	NO	
1.	Orientation	13(100%)	0(0%)0	13(100%)
2.	Mentoring/Coaching	11(84.61%)	2(15.38%)	13(100%)
3.	In-service training	4(30.76%)	9(69.23%)	13(100%)
4.	In-house training	8(61.53%)	5(38.46%)	13(100%)
5.	Job rotation	7(53.86%)	6(46.15%)	13(100%)
6.	Attending workshop	4(30.76)	9(69.23)	13(100)
7.	Attending seminar/conference	2(15.38)	11(84.61)	13(100)

Source: Field survey 2024

Table 2 shows that, Orientation (13:100%), mentoring/coaching (11:84.61%) in-house training, 8(61.53%) and Job rotation (7:53.86%) are the major methods of training of cataloguers in Libraries under study. Attending

workshop received 4(30.76%) responses for Yes and 9(69.23%) indicated No. For attending seminar/conference (2:15.38%) responded yes while 11(84.61%) responded No.

Research Question 3: What are the Impacts of Staff Training on Cataloguers Job Performance in Academic Libraries in MMC?

Table 3: Mean ratings of Impact of Training on Job Performance of Cataloguers in Academic Libraries in MMC.

ITEMS	RESPONSES							
	SA	A	UD	SD	D	mean	S D	Decision
1. In house training equips me with job knowledge and skills to enhance my service	7(53.86)	3(23.07)	3(23.07)	0(0)	0(0)	4.31	.855	Accept
2.. Induction/orientation helps to expose me to library cataloguing procedures for equality service in my library.	3(23.07)	8(61.53)	2(15.28)	0(0)	0(0)	4.38	.641	Accept
3. My supervisors coaching/mentoring makes me more committed.	9(69.23)	4(30.7)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	4.69	.480	Accept
4. Job Rotation increases my experiences in cataloguing tasks.	7(53.86)	4(30.7)	2(15.38)	0(0)	0(0)	4.38	.768	Accept
5. In-service training develops my intellect and skills and prepares me for new responsibilities and challenges	8(61.53)	3(23.07)	2(15.38)	0(0)	0(0)	4.46	.776	Accept
6. Attendance of conferences, seminars, and workshops helps to update my knowledge in cataloguing and to participate in discussion of issues on cataloguing.	6(46.15)	7(53.86)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	4.46	.519	Accept

Source: Field survey 2024: KEY: SA=Strongly Agree A= Agree, UD=Undecided, SD=Strongly Disagree, D=Disagree

The analysis on table 3 revealed that impact of staff training on Cataloguers’ job performance have a mean score above the bench mark mean of 3.50 criterion point on five-point Likert scale. Thus, increase in knowledge and skills for enhanced service (mean=4.31); expose me

to library cataloguing procedures for quality service in my library(mean=4.38); being more committed (mean=4.69); increases my experience in cataloguing tasks.(mean=4.38); developing intellect and skills for new responsibilities and challenges (mean= 4.46));

participation in discussion of issues on cataloguing(mean=4.46). Also, the overall grand mean shows that training impacts job performance of Cataloguers in MMC.

Summary of Major Findings

1. The level of Job performance of cataloguers in Academic libraries in MMC is moderate.
2. The Staff training methods benefitted by cataloguers in Academic libraries in MMC are: Orientation, mentoring/coaching, in-house trainings and that, Workshop, conference/seminar, being rarely employed.
3. There is a significant positive impact of staff training on job performance of cataloguers in the libraries studied.

Discussions

The finding to question one revealed that, job performance is moderate. This is in contrast to findings of Saka and Haruna (2013) and Fajoyonmi (2019) that reported that library personnel's job performance is low. Their performance may be high if cataloguing services is automated. This view is in agreement with of Anyafulu & Okiki' in Eyo (2021) who expressed that a cataloguer can catalogue up-to 15 books in a day manually and that the number would be higher if being catalogued electronically. Unfortunately, the cataloguers are not using Information and Communication Technology (ICT) facilities for cataloguing job as indicated in the analysis in table one (mean = 1.6) which is below the criterion mean of 2.50.

Furthermore, research question two (2) revealed that Orientation, mentoring/coaching, in-house training are the major methods of training of cataloguers in Libraries under study, and that Workshop, conference/seminar, are rarely employed. This may not be unconnected with the cost of sponsorship and attitudes of some cataloguers who do not want to leave their environment. This is in agreement with

Ajidajun (2017) and Shalmalmi, (2022) who reported that training practices like orientation/induction, mentoring, are the most popular method of training employed in most Nigerian Libraries.

The analysis of results on question three (3) revealed that staff training and development has a significant positive impact of cataloguers' job performance. This finding is in agreement with the study of Madukoma, Bamidele & Uneghu (2016) who revealed that cataloguers' job performance was high as a result of trainings such as workshop, seminar, conferences which have significant impact on job performance of cataloguers. Adeleke & Azubugo (2013); Haliru & Sokari (2016); Saka, Oyedum & Song (2016) also uphold same opinion in line with the finding of the study.

Conclusions

The study therefore, concludes that staff training is essential for job performance of cataloguers in academic libraries in Maiduguri, Metropolitan Council, Borno State. However, cataloguers in Library under study are not benefiting from the off-the job training such as Seminars, Conferences and Workshops.

Recommendations

1. Cataloguers in the libraries under study should do their best to raise the level of their job performance by exhibiting efficiency and effectiveness in cataloguing jobs.
2. The Cataloguers should be given sponsorship to attend cataloguing workshops and seminars in order to meetup with the 21st century trends in cataloguing practice.
3. The cataloguers and their libraries' management should continue to keep in mind that trainings if appropriate will impact

positively on job performance of the Cataloguers.

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